

Identity and Womanhood through a Critical Lens: An Exploration of Uzma Aslam Khan's *Trespassing*

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Abstract

In South Asian developing nations, the predominant socio-cultural tendency for male dominance impairs women's circumstances. Women face numerous challenges related to identity formation and gender-based discrimination under patriarchal hegemony. Pakistani society preserves deeply ingrained patriarchal traditions where women's identities are frequently defined through their relationships with men, rendering them constrained, voiceless and marginalized position. However, the awakening of feminist consciousness has brought significant changes in Pakistan concerning women's rights and social status, although the progress remains minimal in comparison to the West. Furthermore, feminist organizations such as the All-Pakistan Women's Association (APWA) have paved pathways for downtrodden women to reclaim their identity and contest patriarchal advances in all spheres of life. Notable contemporary female writers in Pakistani Fiction, including Bapsi Sidhwa, Sara Suleri, Kamila Shamsie, Qaisra Shahraz, Kishwar Naheed, Feryal Ali Gauhar, etc., have initiated a feminist stream in the last few decades. These writers advocate for women's agency, with an emphasis on proactive engagement rather than passive acceptance. This paper examines the feminist struggle for identity and resistance against various predominant socio-economic factors that support patriarchal ideology within urban, educated communities of contemporary Pakistan as depicted in the novel, *Trespassing* by Uzma Aslam Khan. Moreover, this paper aims to expose how selective modernization primarily benefits male-dominated sectors and leadership structures while deliberately maintaining traditional gender hierarchies and excluding women from key opportunities.

Key words: South-Asian Literature, Gender Studies, Identity and Modernism.

Introduction:

"Have you noticed that when men want freedom, the conversation is about the nature of action, violence or non-violence? But when women want freedom, the conversation is about the nature of women, natural or unnatural?" (Khan, 2022, p.166)

These lines reveal the societal double standards in framing and critiquing the liberation movements. The notion of female liberation remains a bone of contention mostly in the South-Asian and Middle-Eastern countries as reflected in the works of literary writers of those particular regions. The issue of female agency and gender-based discrimination remains unresolved in the predominantly patriarchal culture of Third-world nations, including Pakistan, Afghanistan and Bangladesh. In these nations, women's experiences are largely shaped by several intersecting factors such as, class, caste, ethnicity, religion, rural/urban location, disability and sexuality. Gender -based restrictions on women's movement and access to public spaces vary widely across different places and cultures - from strict segregation to relative freedom. Class makes these inequalities worse where elite urban women may have relatively more freedom and privileges than rural poor women within the nation. This research paper investigates the circumstances encountered by Muslim women in Pakistan, a developing state and an Islamic Republic in which Islamic jurisprudence fundamentally shapes the country's constitutional bodies. Pakistani women are often forced to become the repositories of cultures, a

position endowed to them by the so-called 'Fundamentalists,' religiously motivated political opportunists whose intention to restore the traditional Islam of the Prophet's lifetime led them to dig up un-Islamic values and practices of the pre-Islamic era. (Moghissi, 1999, pp. 69-70) Concerning the question of Muslim women's liberation, capitalists, communists and fundamentalists – all use the "trope" of Muslim women to represent their respective ideological frameworks. (Firdous, 2020, p. 45) In the context of the women in Pakistan, a very poignant remark is imperative to mention: "In Pakistan, this ongoing battle involves her sexuality, marriage, mobility, work, dress – so much about which is heard, rarely from herself. Local religious zealots control her in the name of Islam; the West controls her in the name of freedom. She is never consulted: why should she be, when she has no intellect, no artistry? She does not belong to herself but to others, white, brown, and black." (Khan, 2009) Modernization, education and the feminist movement have guaranteed women a few amendments to improve their social condition and empower them. Yet, they are suffering from an identity crisis within the feminine context and their struggle for equality persists. In modern Pakistan, women no longer intend to blindly conform to the conventional cultural and religious norms rooted in selective patriarchal interpretation, as it fails to validate their authentic identity and rights. They challenge the stereotypical social order to create a space for themselves and promote female autonomy, untainted by male hegemony. Needless to mention that a feminist movement in any patriarchy-ingrained society would not win overnight or go along through challenging the regime. Women need to understand the crux of the gender trouble and create an awareness to address the needs of the margins through promoting gender equality. The ongoing growth of feminine consciousness finds centrality in the works of contemporary female writers in Pakistani fiction in English.

Objectives:

This paper aims to highlight the struggle of women regarding the assertion of their identity, sense of autonomy and decision-making power against the predominant socio-economic factors in the urban setup of Pakistan, capping their freedom and making them succumb to the social diktats. This paper will additionally emphasize the pressing need for transformation and opposition to conventional patriarchal authority both within the family and in broader social context. An in-depth analysis of *Trespassing* by Uzma Aslam Khan would help attain the objectives of this research paper.

Uzma Aslam Khan is a critically acclaimed author of Pakistani origin. Five of her novels, including *The Story of Noble Rot* (2001), *Trespassing* (2003), *The Geometry of the God* (2008), *Thinner than Skin* (2012) and *The Miraculous True History of Nomi Ali* (2019), go to her credit. Her fiction addresses a diverse array of thematic concerns, ranging from the political rights of indigenous communities in northern Pakistan and religious fundamentalism to ecological degradation and nuanced human experiences such as love, grief and separation—all framed within the larger context of political upheaval and violence. She also examines various critical factors, including social, religious, economic and political restrictions imposed on women to illustrate their marginalization in her writings.

Trespassing was Uzma Aslam Khan's second novel, published in 2003. This work was translated into fourteen languages across eighteen nations. Adding to her growing list of accolades, it received recognition as a finalist for the 2003 Commonwealth Writers' Prize, Eurasia region. Khan, in *Trespassing*, encodes women's experiences from both upper and lower class and multifarious issues faced by them in both privately and publicly. Further, Khan explores the issues of poverty, social ailments, the transformation of women's identities, class distinction and the endless power struggles between both the sexes. Khan's portrayal of strong-minded women leads, including the protagonist, Riffat Mansoor and her daughter, Dia Mansoor and her worker, Sumbul contest the male-controlled tradition and challenge to usurp man-made social borders. These self-assured women from urban setups endeavor to forge their independent selfhood beyond the confines of traditional roles as mothers, sisters, daughters or wives. They are strongly determined to construct their individual identity distinct from the conventional familial labels.

Khan's *Trespassing* unfolds a complex plot with subtle connections. The story introduces Riffat Mansoor, a reviver of organic dyes, nurturer of silkworms and decisive entrepreneur who chooses to marry out of obligation rather than love. She remains largely unaffected by her husband's indifference

until he is murdered by criminals. During her college years in 1960s London, she develops feelings for Doctor Shafqat, but their romance dissolves upon returning to their homeland, Pakistan. Riffat demonstrates a profound resistance to the authoritarian mindset embodied by an educated figure like Shafqat, ultimately empowering herself through her pursuit of an independent professional identity as a businesswoman. Conversely, Anu, a vociferous mother and silent wife of Shafqat, exemplifies the conventional idea of a submissive housewife through her compliant nature. Anu's son Daanish, a journalist in the making from America, had come to Pakistan to attend his father's funeral. Anu coerces Daanish to accept a marital proposal with Nini. However, Daanish becomes attracted to Dia, Riffat's daughter and Nini's friend. Both Daanish and Dia enjoy their amorous indulgent until Salaamat, a former fisherman, reports their clandestine intimacy to Daanish's mother. The love affair between Daanish and Dia ends in the devastating revelation that they share the same father – Doctor Shafqat.

Methodology:

This research study adopts a descriptive and explanatory approach through employing a qualitative methodology. The findings of this research are derived through the close reading and analysis of primary textual sources, supported by interdisciplinary secondary sources, including books, peer-reviewed journals, articles and web-based resources.

Research Questions:

This research paper sets out to answer the following research questions:

- How does the intersectionality of gender, class and social mobility create different experiences of identity formation and resistance strategies among women in contemporary Pakistan?
- How does selective modernization operate as a patriarchal mechanism that boosts economic and political development while systematically excluding women from accessing the transformative benefits of social progress?

Textual Analysis and Interpretation:

Khan's *Trespassing* endeavors to unravel the gender-based social hierarchy and power dynamics within society. Pakistan remains predominantly a feudal society where women rely heavily on men and are considered subordinate to them. This society demonstrates antagonism toward women and attempts to restrict their freedom. Khan (2003) critiques this persistent conventional ideology and presents her alternative views through using Dia as her spokesperson in the following lines:

Only her mother believed otherwise. She stated that the elders sought to engulf the world in apathy, attempting to stifle any potential advancements for the country. It was all a ploy to keep things working in their own favour. Take marriage, for instance. They wanted it to remain a union that suited them, not the couple. She told Dia the worst thing she could do was listen to that, and perhaps was the only mother in the country to repeatedly warn her to marry only out of love, not obligation. (p. 13)

Here, 'elders' refers to the patriarchy-ingrained attitude within the household that exerts control on individuals, particularly womenfolk. Women are expected to follow the directives of the 'elders' unquestioningly without showing a sign of resistance. However, Riffat, an educated woman, poses a challenge to male supremacy by maintaining a contrary belief and transmitting these principles to her daughter; thereby playing a pivotal role in Dia's identity formation within a feminine context. In this context, Khan expresses her discontent with patriarchal beliefs and their impact on individual's life, especially women. Regardless to mention that 'elders' in person are not to be blamed, but it is the indifferent social structure created by them that is entirely to blame, as all 'elders' around the world are not the same.

Contradictory to Dia and Riffat's characters, Khan exemplifies a compliant character like Dia's friend, Nini, who embraces arranged marriage as an escape route from her stifling domesticated existence. Desperate for a change, Nini eagerly seeks transformation by entering into a matrimonial relationship with Daanish, hardly knowing anything about him. Dia makes every effort to dissuade her friend from marrying a stranger, but Nini remains stubbornly resolute, instead trying to convince Dia to be an ally

in her cause: "Face it Dia, you need a man in your life too, and you won't ever know if the one you pick is better than the one I do." (Khan, 2003, p. 94) Conversely, Dia abhors coerced (arranged) marriage as a ploy for exploitation and consistently advocates for women like Nini to resist patriarchal dominance by claiming female agency rather than yielding to male supremacy. Undoubtedly, the feminist movement in Pakistan has made notable strides in improving women's conditions. It continues to navigate the tensions between religious conservatism and women's rights, working toward legal reform, economic empowerment and the dismantling of deeply rooted patriarchal norms. Yet, women's circumstances remain largely constrained and codified due to persistent socio-political factors. In the text, *Trespassing*, the conversation between Nini and Dia exhibit a conscious understanding of Pakistani women's cloistered reality when Nini vents her frustration to her friend Dia about the restrictions women face in her community. Whether indoors or outside, she feels trapped – either by physical danger or social gossip. Using herself as an example, she highlights how independent women are judged. Burdened with protecting her family's reputation, she questions whether this life can truly be called freedom (Khan, 2003, p. 114). Nini's outbursts reveal how domestic and societal restrictions confine women and stunt their growth. Contrariwise, in Dia's case, maternal influence plays a crucial role in shaping her feminine consciousness, which Nini lacks. Through the exploration of both the characters, Khan demonstrates how women navigate for liberation within strict social structures; their divergent approaches expose the intricate compromises mandated for identity formation and selfhood. However, Khan also suggests that individual awareness alone cannot combat patriarchy; instead, true liberation for women requires collective resistance strategies to dismantle all structures that infringe upon women's agency and autonomy.

Moreover, Khan explores the hierarchical gender dynamics in society, where men occupy domineering positions and women are relegated to voiceless subordination. Khan's *Trespassing* powerfully illustrates the psychological burden of gendered expectations and social surveillance that women face under patriarchy. In the text, when the young lovers, Daanish and Dia share an intimate moment in the cave, both reveal strikingly contrasting sentiments. After indulging in the forbidden act of intimacy outside marriage, Dia is tormented by a sense of fear and premonition, dreading all the potential consequences of her transgression. She recalls news stories of women killed by their own family members for far less than what she has already done. Living in a society where a woman's reputation defines her worth, she has internalized constant self-consciousness as a means of survival. Yet, in this moment, she begins to shed some of that burden: the guilt of lying to loved ones, her doubts about Daanish and her fear of being mocked by men like Khurram and Salaamat. Though she also has acknowledged that this deeply rooted fear and conditioning can never be fully escaped (Khan, 2003, p. 289). Contrariwise, Daanish, as a man, remains untroubled and at peace, savoring each moment of intimacy. "But Daanish began massaging the knot that had been building inside her ever since their first tryst ... Daanish's fingers probed expertly." (p.289-290) Daanish's gendered identity shields him from social criticism despite their shared transgression of societal norms. Dia later resolves to resist the prescribed codes of femininity and embraces desires over restraints; thereby making a daunting declaration of selfhood. And, she states, "She was twenty years old and ready to be something more than the repository of her family's honor. She was twenty years old and ready to be loved." (p. 290)

In addition, Khan exposes how patriarchal authority operates through contradiction. *Trespassing* effectively illustrates the contradictory nature of selective modernization, which embraces progressive ideals but vetoes women's freedom as a foreign import. Riffat Mansoor, in a heated exchange with Shafqat, challenges the latter's selective vision of modernization. While Shafqat advocates for democracy, healthcare, and a free press, she exposes his hypocrisy. Shafqat resists women's equal presence in public spaces, dismissing it as a foreign influence that will "take longer" to accept. She confronts him directly, pointing out that his idea of progress conveniently excludes women's freedom. When pushed further, he openly declares that domestic responsibilities are solely her duty, while his role is to fight for freedom – revealing a deep contradiction where he champions liberty for society but denies it to women within his own home (Khan, 2003, pp. 421-423). Thus, the confrontation between Shafqat and Riffat exposes the contradiction within modernizing societies that embrace political and

economic growth while deliberately preserving patriarchal structures to subordinate women and continue to serve male interests. In this regard, Moghissi's notion of 'Modernity' becomes particularly relevant. Moghissi draws a clear distinction between the two concepts of 'Modernization' and 'Modernity'. In the context of the Middle East and the Third World, modernization is understood as industrialization, capitalism and economic growth driven by multinational corporations; controlled by authoritarian elites and serving the interests of the privileged few. Modernity, on the other hand, is a far broader concept that embraces a wide spectrum of cultural, political, and economic dimensions (Firdous, 2020, p. 12). In further elaborating on the dimensions of modernity in the Western world, Moghissi (1999) argues, "The legal, social and cultural rights which women enjoy in the West, as compared with their sisters elsewhere, are a consequence of the recognition of women's full citizenship status (personhood) – that is, equality before the law and equality in law." (p. 96) These criteria suggest that Pakistan, a patriarchal developing nation, has not yet embraced modernity. Rather, what they encounter is a superficial and distorted form of modernization that is devoid of the intellectual underpinnings of modernism and fundamentally disconnected from the true essence of modernity (Moghissi, 1999, p.54). In *Trespassing*, even London's liberal environment failed to leave an impact on Shafqat's mind and reform his hegemonic views that demand female submission. He dismisses Riffat's claim for Pakistani women's liberation as immature and irrational. However, Riffat, shaped by modernist ideals, boldly challenges this dominant perspective and asserts her selfhood and dignity on the basis of equal social standing. That the same struggles for women's liberation and equality that defined the 1960s continue to persist today speaks to the continuing nature of gender inequality.

Trespassing also highlights the societal pressure encountered by women from lower economic strata, who undergo the pain of being doubly marginalized due to their exclusion from mainstream society and their misfortune to live with frugal means. In rural Pakistan, these lower-class women are often sent to work as domestic help in upper-class households to support their families. In the text, Sumbul, who works at Riffat's farm, represents these marginalized lower-class women with multi-dimensional challenges. In one of the passages from *Trespassing*, Khan captures the complex intersectionality of Sumbul's profound struggle when her child is dying, yet she chooses to remain at Riffat's farm rather than returning home. It happens this way because home offers her no comfort, but only relentless domestic labour, an abusive husband, an overbearing mother-in-law, financial exploitation by neighbours and poor living conditions. She cannot even enjoy a quiet moment alone without being shamed for it. The farm, despite the grief it holds, is paradoxically the only place where she finds any degree of peace (Khan, 2003, p. 427). The word 'Home', in her context, poses a threat to her autonomous identity and curbs her freedom, while her employment as a farm worker actually provides her mental peace, security and respite from domestic oppression. Sumbul's hardships show how gender, class and family structure intersect to trap a woman. Sumbul is exposed to different forms of exploitation as a woman (by husband and mother-in-law), as a worker (supporting extended network) and as a lower-class individual. Studies suggest that female-headed households are found in the poorest strata of society with women having little to no education or skills related to work outside the household sphere (Isran, 2012). Poverty and violence are interconnected issues affecting women within patriarchal structures using violence as an instrument of control (Tarar & Pulla, 2014). In the text, Sumbul's adversities echo the challenges faced by lower-class women in Pakistan, who negotiate different exploitative situations, choosing the least harmful one for survival. Her situation reflects deeply entrenched patriarchal structures that particularly disadvantage women who lack economic resources to overcome social and cultural barriers.

Uzma Aslam Khan is among a broader group of female writers from India and Pakistan who have collectively shaped a distinct feminist literary tradition. These authors engage with recurring concerns such as the construction of female identity, the pervasive influence of patriarchal structures, the tension between inherited customs and contemporary values and women's ongoing struggle to assert independence within the constraints of their respective cultural and social contexts. Indian writers including Shashi Deshpande, Anita Desai, Nayantara Sehgal, Bama and Arundhati Roy have established a distinctive feminist tradition exploring issues of intersectionality, caste discrimination,

Dalit feminism and diasporic experiences in contemporary India (Ray, 2018). Notable contemporary Pakistani female writers, including Bapsi Sidhwa, Sara Suleri, Kamila Shamsie, Qaisra Shahraz, Kishwar Naheed, Feryal Ali Gauhar, etc., scrutinized the gender dynamics and addressed themes of patriarchal oppression, urban women's experiences and the complex navigation between tradition and modernity (Malik et al., 2022). All these writers have spoken out against various socio-cultural factors that contribute to the marginalization of women, using a unique perspective shaped by female literary sensibility.

Conclusion:

Nonetheless, Uzma Aslam Khan's attempt to reconstruct a modern Pakistan in a more gender-inclusive manner is commendable. Khan's *Trespassing* serves as a prime example of feminist literary discourse by exploring political violence and societal brutalization while challenging patriarchal structures through complex female characters. Her characters, Riffat Mansoor, Dia and Sumbul are the perfect embodiment of strong, independent women of modern Pakistan, who boldly defy man-made social boundaries, though paying a hefty price, but survive through self-empowerment. These women challenge deeply entrenched social practices such as forced and arranged marriage, as well as the systematic exclusion of Muslim women from public life. Their literary and social activism is driven by a sense of urgency, positioned as a necessary step toward progressive change and the broader modernisation of their societies. In *Trespassing*, all the female leads collectively advocate for a transformative change in women's conditions across both public and private domains while actively asserting female identity and empowerment against systemic oppression. Literary critic Muneeza Shamsie has situated Khan's writing within a broader feminist literary movement in Pakistan, recognising it as part of a collective effort to interrogate and subvert prevailing gender norms and expectations (Ali et al., 2022). Regarding the portrayal of female characters in *Trespassing*, Kezia Poole states, "Characters show that being a woman in modern Pakistan is not a simple choice of looking back or moving forward, of submitting or resisting, but an experience shaped by the many unique and conflicting factors that make up a person's life." (Poole, n.d.) Khan openly critiques the ways in which religious, social, political, and cultural forces shape and reinforce conventional attitudes in both men and women. Beyond this, she seeks to demonstrate that the challenges faced by Muslim women in Pakistan are rooted primarily in societal structures and practices rather than in religious doctrine or moral prescription.

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